

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D2.2 Collaborathon Report & Exploitation Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The D2.2 is dedicated to the report of actions regarding the implementation of the *Collaborathon* initiatives & Exploitation Plan. This deliverable is the result of the work developed by F6S as the leader of Task 2.3 *European-wide Collaborathon organisation and implementation*. This Task was foreseen in the GA to be implemented within three months, between the second month (M2) and the fourth month (M4) of the project. This task is under the Work Package 2 led by HAM.

This deliverable is the result of the activities developed in the Task 2.3 and it impacts directly on the Task 2.4 *Collaborathon results exploitation*, to be implemented in the following months - M5-M12 – by F6S along with the respective INTEGER project partners.

This deliverable goal is to present and describe steps and implementation of actions that resulted from a co-creation process that involved project partners, as well as the key stakeholders, at a regional and inter-regional level, for a wider vision of the Healthy living and Social innovation ecosystem, in the Project target regions (Krakow; Catalonia; Hamburg) in order to identify common challenges and barriers from early stages for integration of social innovators into innovation ecosystems developing, map and support social innovators.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	6
SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	7
2 INTRODUCTION	8
2.1 Background and aim	8
2.2 Structure of the deliverable	9
3 Methodology	10
3.1 Key Stakeholders pre-event	11
3.1.1 Goal and outcomes.....	11
3.1.2 Before the online event.....	13
3.1.3 On the online event.....	14
3.2 Stakeholders event - Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together!	15
3.2.1 Goals and outcomes	18
3.2.2 Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together! Session 1	18
3.2.3 Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together! Session 2	20
4 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables	35
5 Lessons learned	37
6 CONCLUSIONS	39
REFERENCES	41
ANNEX 1 - INTEGER GA	41
ANNEX 2 - F6S Power Point from the INTEGER Kick off Meeting	42
ANNEX 3 - Guidelines Key Stakeholder Pre-event	45
ANNEX 4 - F6S Power Points from Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together! Session 1	46
ANNEX 5 - F6S Power Points from Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together! Session 2	47
ANNEX 6 - Report questions to Facilitators for Key stakeholders work outputs	48
ANNEX 7 - Report questions to Facilitators for Key stakeholders work outputs	49

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. TASKS & DELIVERABLES & ITS INTERCONNECTION WITH ACTIVITIES.	9
FIGURE 2. THE TOOLS USED IN THE CONTEXT OF THE TASK 2.3 METHODOLOGY OF IMPLEMENTATION	11
FIGURE 3. THE LIST OF STAKEHOLDERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE KEY STAKEHOLDER EVENT	12
FIGURE 4. SLIDE PRESENTED TO INTEGER PARTNERS IN ORDER TO ORGANISE THE AGENDA AND MAP/INVITE THE STAKEHOLDER	16
FIGURE 5. THE PLANNED FLOW OF ACTIONS IN THE INNOVATION 4HEALTHY LIVING LET’S HACK TOGETHER! EVENT	18
FIGURE 6. GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR THE SUBGROUPS DISCUSSION PRESENTED IN SESSION 1	19
FIGURE 7. THE LIST OF STAKEHOLDERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION 2 OF THE INNOVATION 4HEALTHY LIVING LET’S HACK TOGETHER! EVENT – 40 PARTICIPANTS IN TOTAL	21
FIGURE 8. THE FIRST SOLUTION PROPOSAL FOR CHALLENGE 1	24
FIGURE 9. THE SECOND SOLUTION PROPOSAL FOR CHALLENGE 1	25
FIGURE 10. THE THIRD SOLUTION PROPOSAL FOR CHALLENGE 1	26
FIGURE 11. THE FOURTH SOLUTION PROPOSAL FOR CHALLENGE 1	26
FIGURE 12. THE FIFTH SOLUTION PROPOSAL FOR CHALLENGE 1	27
FIGURE 13. THE BOARD TO COLLECT IDEAS FROM THE BRAINSTORMING EXERCISE IN THE SUBGROUP OF CHALLENGE 2, LED BY HAM	28
FIGURE 14. THE SOLUTION PROPOSED AND THE OBJECTIVE AND RESOLUTION ON CHALLENGE 3	30
FIGURE 15. THE TARGET PUBLIC IDENTIFIED IN CHALLENGE 3	31
FIGURE 16. THE IDENTIFIED SYNERGIES TO BE IMPLEMENTED IN THE SOLUTION PRESENTED IN CHALLENGE 3	32
FIGURE 17. THE CHANGE AND SOLUTION IDENTIFIED IN THE PROPOSED SOLUTION FOR CHALLENGE 3	32
FIGURE 18. ANALYSIS OF THE SUSTAINABLE AND REPLICABLE ASPECTS OF THE SOLUTION PROPOSED FOR CHALLENGE 3	33
FIGURE 19. SDG GOAL AND ITS LINK TO THE SOLUTION PROPOSED FOR CHALLENGE 3	34
FIGURE 20. INTERACTION BETWEEN ACTIVITIES IN WP2 AND WP3	35
FIGURE 21. INTEGER MODEL CORE GROUP SPACE IN THE PLATFORM	38

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. THE OPTIONS PRESENTED TO THE KEY STAKEHOLDERS IN THE GOOGLE FORM PRE-EVENT REGARDING THE CHALLENGE/NEED IN THEIR REGION IN THE HEALTHY LIVING& WELL-BEING ECOSYSTEM	12
TABLE 2. GUIDELINES FOR THE CHALLENGE SUBGROUP WORK OUTCOME	19

SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D.	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T.	Task
WP	Work-Package
4Helix	Quadruple helix
M	Month
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
GA	General Assembly

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

The deliverable 2.2 *Collaborathon Report & Exploitation Plan* is based on the work of the Task 2.3 *European-wide Collaborathon organisation and implementation*, led by F6S, within the WP2, *Learning For 4h Collaboratory Co-Creation*, led by HAM. The strategy and implementation of this task was the result of a team collaboration, led by F6S and with the participation of URV, i2CAT, HAM, KTP, and UJ. Also, the partner SHINE had an important role, even if indirect and transversal, in all the image/design creation and communication and dissemination of activities regarding the preparation and follow up of the actions implemented under the T2.3.

As a contextualisation, the overall objective of the WP2, as stated in the Grant Agreement, is to:

- 1) Early exchange lessons learned, experiments and success factors on the integration of 3H and 4H actors in the three participating regions
- 2) Raise awareness about the need to create an EU Collaboratory (sustainable and challenge-driven focused on the field of healthy living)
- 3) Establish a pilot INTEGER community, merging active regional actors with relevant European stakeholders, projects and initiatives, to co-design the working 3H & 4H integration mechanisms and processes.

This task, as well as the WP2, relies heavily on the engagement of the regional partners of INTEGER - Catalonia (SP); Hamburg (GE); Krakow (POL) - as their contribution as real active actors in their regions are essential to the success and quality of the outputs.

This task is the first contribution to the overall goal of implementing a transition from the knowledge triangle to a dynamic 4 helix in order to enable the bridge from social innovation to the business market, reinforcing the relations between regional and trans-regional actors. The actions in the context of this task, as part of a wider Work Package, provides the base to a joint work on initiatives that answers to common needs, between actors of different sectors, as well as from different regions, and that can be replicated.

Following up the main “umbrella” goals from the WP2 and the INTEGER project, the Task 2.3 *European-wide Collaborathon organisation and implementation*, was built following the main 3 objectives:

1. Build up an international event for INTEGER 4H Collaboratory model co-creation;
2. Promote the event across the EU;
3. Support social innovators in their preparation for the event
 - Enable access to the INTEGER common platform
 - Provide & collect relevant information and the agenda in advance

- Support stakeholders between the 17th and the 25th of May, namely through designated facilitators per challenge group (of transregional characteristics), as the main contact in INTEGER and as experts in social innovation.

Figure 1. Tasks & Deliverables & its interconnection with activities.

Figure 1 describes the succession of the events that will support building the interaction activities, mainly in WP2 and WP3, under the tasks led by FS6, as interconnected and as a *crescendum* of actions that will culminate in a final event under the WP3, as a result of the activities initiated in the WP2, namely under the Task 2.3.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is focused on the *Collaborathon* activity and the outcomes of this initiative, namely the exploitation plan, that is linked with the follow-up WP and T. from the INTEGER Project, as every action is interlinked between themselves. These activities from task 2.3 lay down the foundation, as the first action for engaging stakeholders, to the wider strategy of implementation of the INTEGER project.

The deliverable presents the methodologies and tools used to build an international and inter-regional event for INTEGER 4H Collaboratory model co-creation, namely through the following activities, as previewed in the GA:

- Ecosystems developing a peer-to-peer approach to join digital economic and social innovation;
- Supporting social innovation entrepreneurs and start-ups. Connecting these with successful social innovation SMEs, Investors, corporates and other actors within the ecosystem that could provide direct support or benefit from their innovation;
- Promote the event across the EU, create buzz around it and invite 20 active partners from the 3H and 4H in the three INTEGER participating regions. (WP5);
- Support social innovators in their preparation for the event;
- Build portfolio of inspirational cases and existing MVPS

2 Methodology

Human-centred design (HCD) methodology was used to support the INTEGER's model creation and development. This is the chosen methodology taking into account that it focuses on individuals feedback to design, develop and manage the process. The goal is to address challenges through the active participation of all actors involved. The methodological approach starts by observing the needs and challenges with its contextual framework, either at a regional or transregional level, and generates ideas, as solutions, from various perspectives. These solutions proposals are then synthesised into potential solutions and subsequently transformed into prototypes.

This bottom-up approach, by consulting the actors for inputs and solutions top-down, starts by reaching out first to the identified key actors by INTEGER partners, as the most relevant players of the well-being and healthy ecosystem regionally. These key players were the first to integrate their views and kick start the process that was followed up by connecting and consulting the several actors of the 3Helix from the 3 regions in the INTEGER project.

The tools used to collect and manage information were mainly online-based, as they meant to reach out to several regions simultaneously.

As a first step of consultation with the actors a google form was sent, firstly to key stakeholders, named by the partners, as the most relevant player in their ecosystem due to their representation in the sector, as well as the work implemented, and the network established. We asked these key stakeholders to select the main challenges/needs in their region. A follow up online meeting with them and representatives of the three regions in the INTEGER project took place, where the results of the form were presented, and break-out rooms, per region, were created so that they could deepen the discussion between themselves. The sub-groups were composed by stakeholders from the same region, from Hamburg, to Krakow and Catalonia, however they were based and active in different regional locations.

As a result of the discussion in the three subgroups, 3 main challenges were presented. These challenges were the base of the work developed in the two additional sessions, in the context of the ***Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*** event for a larger group of actors that represented the 3helix from the three regions. These stakeholders reunited in breakout rooms, as well, running simultaneously, to break it into smaller groups, from various regions and sectors. The division of the stakeholders was based on the interest of the actor in the challenge proposed. This moment served as an enabler for discussions and was supported with the use of dynamic joint boards (Miro) to share ideas and reach solutions proposals and managed by facilitators from the INTEGER project.

The INTEGER online platform was the sustainable crucial tool used for engagement of actors in the project, which supported the exchange of profiles, providing an online portfolio of organisations, enabling a one-stop place for all stakeholders to actively involve, receive and share information, in one single online platform. The platform was used to:

- the integration of all stakeholders for the upcoming initiatives as previewed in the INTEGER Project, in synergy between WP's, namely with the WP4 *Integer 4h Model & EU Healthy Living Collaboratory Deployment*;

- 3 channels of discussion and co-creation process, per challenges, used between session 1 and session 2, in the context of the ***Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*** event
- Internal channel of communication between the INTEGER facilitators (Facilitators's corner)

Figure 2. The tools used in the context of the Task 2.3 methodology of implementation

The dissemination and invitation of 20 active partners from the 3H and 4H in the three INTEGER participating regions were done through direct emails contacts of the regional INTEGER partners and the results of the event were also shared in social media & website, as well as in the project's newsletter. The newsletter was sent by SHINE to 600 contacts and partners distributed it to their contacts, and further disseminated it through social media channels.

The several events and the way they unfolded, as well as the tools used, were viewed as a step-by-step engagement and as a starting point of the project, taking into account that this task started in the second month of the project and lasted only for two months.

2.1 Key Stakeholders pre-event

2.1.1 Goal and outcomes

As a first action in Task 2.3 a pre-event was organised with the goal of gathering a group of identified Key stakeholders from the 3Helix of the 3 regional ecosystems represented in the project, from Hamburg to Kraków and Catalonia, partners of INTEGER project. These regional stakeholders were invited by the INTEGER project to participate & contribute to an online INTEGER Pre-Model Event on Healthy living and Social innovation and to discuss and identify the main challenge in the healthy living and well-being ecosystem in their regions.

In Figure 3 you can analyse the diversity of areas that the Key stakeholders come from - the 3H area. You can also analyse the names of the organizations/entities that were contacted and participated. Note that if a name is repeated, it is because there was more than one participant from the same entity, as is the case of the Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs. We will not share any other information, such as position or contact for a matter of data protection (GDPR). However, by sharing this summarised information it is possible to have an idea regarding the diversity and number of participants per region during the Key Stakeholders event. This was the first event created to start the design of a joint strategy, as this was intended to be a smaller event to focus on the vision, experience and input of major players identified by the INTEGER partners. These Key stakeholders were invited by INTEGER to be part of this focused first event to choose and propose 3 challenges to be discussed in the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*, that will gather a wider group of stakeholders from the three regions. The Key stakeholders come from the health and well-being ecosystems and were selected by the INTEGER partners, as the main player on their regional ecosystem, based on their experience and knowledge of the ecosystem of social innovation. One of the main criteria was their impact and experience in their sector in the region and in the overall ecosystem.

4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Krakow		
Other	Regional	Cluster Life Science Krakow
Other	Regional	Cluster Life Science Krakow
Civic Society	National	Foundation Internationaler Bund Polska
Civic Society	Regional	Foundation Supporting Education Archezja
Government	Regional	Regional Center for Social Policy
Government	Local	Municipality of Kraków/City's center of Social Assistance
Government	Local	Municipality of Kraków/City's center of Social Assistance
Civic Society	National	FRDL MISTiA
Civic Society	National	FRDL MISTiA
Industry	Local	Parenting Technologies
Other	Regional	Center of Technology Transfer Jagiellonian University
Hamburg		
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs
Other	Regional	Hamburg Investment Bank
Academia	Regional	University Hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf
Industry	Regional	Philips GmbH
Civic Society	Regional	LIDO – Lebensfreude • Innovativ • Digital • vor Ort
Catalonia		
Industry	National	Bax & Company
Industry	National	Bax & Company
Civic Society	National	iSocial Foundation
Industry	National	Me Mima Baby
Academia	Regional	BAL. Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili
Academia	National	Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa
Industry	National	Giromed Institute
Civic Society	Local	AEMA Foundation
Civic Society	Local	AEMA Foundation
Government	Regional	ASPCAT. Catalanian Government Public Health Agency
Other	Regional	Independent - Self Employe
International Stakeholders		
Civic Society	International	AGE PLATFORM EUROPE

Figure 3. The list of stakeholders that participated in the Key Stakeholder event

The Key Stakeholders event was the first event promoted between regional stakeholders in the INTEGER project, a first opportunity to start a conversation and engage directly with the main players of the regional ecosystems. This would also give the INTEGER partners the opportunity to benefit from these stakeholders' contributions and to kickstart a collaborathon that aimed to engage along the project stakeholders from the social innovation 3Helix in the sector of healthy living and well-being.

2.1.2 Before the online event

Prior to the online pre-event, the Key Stakeholders were invited to fill in a short Google form for the identification of a healthy living & well-being challenge in their region. The questions started by assessing their profile, as their sector and region and finally the identification of a main challenge in their region, based on topics identified in the study visits by INTEGER partners – same proposal to all regional partners. The question presented about the challenge was: **“What is, in your view, the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region? Taking into consideration physical, mental and social well-being.”** The options given to answer the question were presented in the table below.

What is, in your view, the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region? Taking into consideration physical, mental and social well-being.	
1.	Housing
2.	Transportation
3.	Food & Nutrition
4.	Outdoor spaces & Buildings
5.	Community support & Health services
6.	Communication & Information
7.	Civic participation & Employment
8.	Social inclusiveness & Participation
9.	Other (providing free text option)

Table 1. The options presented to the Key Stakeholders in the Google form pre-event regarding the challenge/need in their region in the healthy living & well-being ecosystem

In line with the WHO dimensions, the identification of the challenges, through their answers, helped the INTEGER project to assess the landscape and have a starting point of discussion during the online Key Stakeholders meeting, a pre-meeting before a wider stakeholders meeting.

The Task 2.3 leader received the incoming replies and produced several graphics to be presented during the online meeting with the Key Stakeholders. The regional partners made the follow up along with F6S, on the reminders, answering additional questions and sending all needed information for the event participation. The Key stakeholders were asked to appoint a representative with decision-making power to be present and participate in the pre-event for Key Stakeholders.

2.1.3 On the online event

During the online event the INTEGER project was presented as well as the methodology of the event, the goal of this initiative as well as the way the INTEGER would use their input- to be used as a proposal of challenges for the stakeholders' event, in order to present solutions and brainstorm.

The F6S presented the results of the Google form, namely the sector of work of the Key Stakeholders and their Regions, as provided in Annex 2¹, so that all participants could have an idea of the profile of the overall participants. Additionally, it was presented to the Key Stakeholders the **selection of challenges, the most votes per region, based on the Table one option, as well as per sector and per region.**

After this first presentation of the profile and choices of challenges per region, the main group of Key Stakeholders were divided into 3 groups, one subgroup per region, and were sent into breakout rooms. These small rooms served as a starting point to connect different stakeholders from the 4Helix of the regions giving them the opportunity to discuss the results of the Google form in their region and agree to present 1 (one) challenge that represents them. To reach this decision each subgroup had an appointed regional facilitator from INTEGER project, allocated taking into consideration its regional familiarity. I2Cat facilitated the Catalonia subgroup, for example. The facilitator supported the moderation of the debate based on common guidelines that helped to reach a tangible and aligned result (Annex 3²).

The methodology step implemented at this stage were:

1. Mapping of the relevant ecosystem actors and networks per region Catalonia (SP); Hamburg (GE); Krakow (POL) & internationally
2. Asking key stakeholders for inputs to identify common challenges and barriers from early stages for integration of social innovators into innovation in the healthy living and well-being ecosystem
3. Inviting to participate on a follow-up closed meeting in order to decide on 3 main challenges, per 3 subgroups divided regionally
4. Engaging the key stakeholders into a discussion, sharing experiences and views regionally and inter-regional facilitated by one regional representative (3 in total) of the INTEGER project
5. Inviting the key stakeholders to join the follow up event that would gather all stakeholders from the three different regions into a *collaborathon* model and have one spoke person presenting

The outcome of this first meeting was the definition of 3 challenges, **identified regionally, to be discussed at a transregional & trans-sectoral level in the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* that followed up.** These were the 3 challenges selected by the subgroups:

- **Kraków identified challenge (1):** How to channel the unused potential of an ageing population in the regions, particularly in the cities?
- **Hamburg identified challenge (2):** Improve the lack of transparency & promote a better communication between sectors.
- **Catalonia identified challenge (3):** Health & wellness for Life. Specific but aligned actions to improve life quality.

¹ F6S Power Point from the INTEGER Kick off Meeting

² Guidelines Key Stakeholder Pre-event

The outcome of the event *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* was to present the 3 challenges identified for discussion to a wider audience that would gather more stakeholders from the 4 & 3Helix from the 3 regions. A *collaboratory* event, that was used as a first test on a model event, a learning process for the follow-up initiatives of INTEGER, named *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*. The main aim of this follow-up event was to engage the 3Helix participants and to present solutions in the areas of health and well-being, to be analysed the challenges beyond the regional view but in a trans-regional view.

2.2 Stakeholders event - Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!

More than 20 active partners from the 3H and 4H in the three INTEGER participating regions were invited to participate in the model event, named by the Project partners as *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* This event took place in two separate days, on the 17th and the 25th of May 2023, online.

The objective of this event can be summarised into 4 objectives:

- **Objective 1:** Foster a culture of openness;
- **Objective 2:** Promote the use of collaborative platforms and networks to strengthen communication channels between the 4Helix;
- **Objective 3:** Encourage cross-sector partnerships & initiates towards social innovation;
- **Objective 4:** Enhance stakeholder engagement.

The *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* Event, as mentioned previously, was divided into two online events, one meeting took place online on the 17th of May and a second and final event on the 25th of May. These two moments involve stakeholders from the quadruple helix from the healthy living ecosystem from the local/regional innovation ecosystems in the project: Catalonia (SP); Hamburg (GER) and Krakow (POL). These stakeholders were invited to gather and present transversal & replicable solutions to the challenges identified and selected by Key Stakeholders pre-event from the 4Helix in the healthy living ecosystem and based on their experience in their region.

In between the two meetings the participants of the event were integrated in the INTEGER platform, where their profile was shared with the other participants, and they could follow up the conversations that started in the first session of the event in the 17th of May up until the 25th of May. However, they would still be part of the INTEGER platform if they wish in order to continue to be part of the process and participate in the following events and activities in the Project. The idea of **adding the participants to the INTEGER platform was presented as an added value for the participants is being part of a vibrant 'glocal' community building long-term collaborations in physical, virtual or hybrid modes, along the Project events and initiatives.** This would be the main exploitation and sustainable action that would result from this task.

The *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* is one important step in the several initiatives that INTEGER is implementing to build a 4Helix Col-laboratory model and to solve real problems with agents of the 4Helix in the 3 regions involved. All INTEGER regional partners were asked to invite between 20 to 35 stakeholders in their network. You can analyse the methodology of the event presented in the following Figure.

Model event for INTEGER 4H Collaboratory

Figure 4. Slide presented to INTEGER partners in order to organise the agenda and map/invite the stakeholder

Each participant on the ***Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*** event had to select (through the project platform) 1 of the 3 previously defined challenges by Key Stakeholders, not taking the region into account but the challenge itself, considered more linked to their vision, ambition, need, interests and expectations regarding the healthy living ecosystem, in their region but also in a European view. The discussion at this stage has gone beyond the regional scoop, driving the stakeholders to engage in a transregional debate and decision making process between diverse sectors and regions.

During the event, the participant stakeholder joined an inter-regional group of discussion where they explored and debated together social innovation solutions with other European peers from diverse regions (from the 3 of the Project), sectors (3Helix), experiences, needs, offer and view.

The 3 main challenges were presented, as well as their rationale, by one of the Key Stakeholders that participated in the pre-event and that we summarise below:

- **Challenge 1:**

How to channel the unused potential of an ageing population in the regions, particularly in the cities? (Krakow)

Some lines about the challenge proposal: Not enough use of the potential of an ageing population (regardless of citizenship) and it is a waste of their experience and wisdom. Social innovation could be a way to activate older people, the role of civil society also can play a great role in this process, to make the older person not be excluded in a digital and fast paced society.

- **Challenge 2:**

Improve the lack of transparency & promote better communication between sectors (Hamburg)

Some lines about the challenge proposal: The goal is to “improve the lack of transparency and promote a better communication among sectors and actors” and do it through several manner having as a goal to

improve the connection and relation between existing and successful projects, as well as between diverse type of actors and between diverse ecosystem, in different Regions.

○ **Challenge 3:**

Health & Wellness for Life. Specific but aligned actions to improve life quality (Catalonia)

Some lines about the challenge proposal: “we should be focused on the whole life for long-term influence considering the different locations, needs or ages in order to apply the different solutions within nutrition, physical activity, air quality (pollution), social and labour inclusion, etc.”

The identification of the challenges was a first step of a process that had several steps to identify the challenge at a regional level and put into light the need for solutions to push to the launch of real, identified solutions for the social innovation challenges in and beyond their regions.

The expected outcome from the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let’s Hack together! event was to co-identify and/or co-design solutions, minimum viable products and services (especially those that can be common, transversal and replicable) coming from social innovation with a focus to address the difficulty to reach out to the business-driven innovation side and vice versa.

Figure 5. The timeline of the actions in the context of the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let’s Hack together! event

The stakeholders were invited to contribute to this event during 2 online moments and follow up an online ongoing discussion in the INTEGER platform, within their chosen groups per challenge and the flow of work between the first session and the second session was summarised in the following points:

Figure 5. The planned flow of actions in the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let’s Hack together! event

These actions were followed by the presentation of sustainable actions of follow up on the context of INTEGER project, namely on the context of the WP4 activities.

2.2.1 Goals and outcomes

We can summarise the goals of the stakeholders' working groups into these 6 main points:

Identify social innovation solutions

- Better identify social innovation solutions for real needs, channel them to getting more sustainable funding and greater long-term impact;

Overcome gaps

- Overcome the existing gap between social and business-driven innovations;

Dynamics to include the social innovation in regional innovation ecosystems

- Include in a more decisive manner the social innovation in the European calls (e.g. Horizon Europe, European Innovation Council);

Foster 4 Helix dynamics

- Foster more sustainable and functional 4helix dynamics with better governance

Build 4H relations

- The building of interpersonal relationships is crucial to enable the co-creation of new quadruple helix dynamics

Motivation and involvement

- Regular involvement in the creation of new content that can be enriching for the whole community to motivate the engagement of stakeholders in the three regions

2.2.2 Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Session 1

During Session 1 we had the participation of over 40 stakeholders from the 3 regions of INTEGER Project represented, from the 4-helix ecosystem of the well-being and healthy living ecosystem. This was the moment to reunite with some of the stakeholders that participated in previous INTEGER study visits, namely in the Key Stakeholders pre-event, as well as to engage new stakeholders that were in contact for the first time with INTEGER Project. Therefore, we had a first moment to present an overview of the INTEGER Project in this first session and its goals, as it was an introductory, initial event.

In this session, we showcased the methodology that led us to the 3 challenges that had been previously chosen and decided by the Key Stakeholder. The results were presented through one representative from each of the 3 groups so that this peer could explain the rationale behind the proposal of challenge and why this need was relevant not only from a regional perspective, as well as it has transversal characteristics that may be relevant to all regions as a challenge in the well-being and healthy living ecosystem.

In this first session, it was also important the presentation of:

- the INTEGER platform, as the virtual space for building the community, to showcase the benefits and advantages of being in the platform

- follow steps to manage and navigate it, (with the live presentation of the platform in the form of screen sharing and Q&A space for participants), and
- the sustainability and exploitation plan for the participants,

- About **10** stakeholders per subgroup: **transregional and trans sectorial**
- **1 to 2 facilitator** per challenge, managing the subgroup
- Each subgroup defines a **Head lead to do a pitch elevator at the 25th of May (5m)**
- Development of the solution is made based on the **guideline points** (to be presented next), coordinated and verified by facilitator

Figure 6. General guidelines for the subgroups discussion presented in Session 1

The participants were divided into subgroups per challenge that they chose in the Google form before the event. The groups had to be balanced in number and also in regional representation and in sector representation, whenever possible. Initially, it was previewed, as seen in the image presented during the event, to create two subgroups per challenge, however, this was adjusted after the first session and the decision was to keep one subgroup per challenge, even if we had to include 13 to 14 participants per group, instead of the initially planned maximum 10 per group. All the other points, as stated in Figure 7 remained the same.

The subgroups had to follow up common guidelines so that the final solutions presented could ensure that they focused on tangible and practical solutions. The common guidelines for the group outcome were presented and moderated by the named facilitators, and partners from INTEGER Project, one per region in the project.

The following questions, in the table, were provided to the participants in session 1 and the indication was that the solution should be able to reply in a resumed, but clear way, by each sub-group on the chosen challenge, to all of the questions. The result from the subgroup discussions had to be presented to all participants in session 2.

1. What is the objective and the resolution of your solution? Please focus specifically on how the social and the business-driven innovations can join forces to engage in a clear implementation and the possible solution to be used.

2. Who is/are the target people/entities/ of your solution?

3. What are the synergies that will be boosted among actors from the 4Helix to contribute to the solution implementation?
4. What change will this solution bring, as an added value for the well-being and healthy living domain?
5. Is the solution identified sustainable & replicable?
6. In what way does your solution reply to the SDG goals?

Table 2. Guidelines for the Challenge subgroup work outcome

The objective of this guideline with common questions is to be sure that the result was tangible, replicable, and practical and that all the subgroup results would be homogeneous.

2.2.3 Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Session 2

The goal of the second event of the ***Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*** was to gather conclusions and finalise group discussions with joint outputs that can be used as a base of discussion during the events to be promoted regionally.

Another objective of session 2 was to reach a solution to support the social innovators to reach the market with solutions to challenges that the ecosystem struggled with, at a regional level but at a transnational level as well. The promotion of live discussion in breakout rooms during session 2 enabled the follow-up of the discussions initiated in session 1. The allocated time to this discussion was essential to complete what was started in session 1 and followed up in the platform, in view to finalize and present to all participants in session 2 a solution for the identified challenges by the Key stakeholders.

Challenge 1: How to channel the unused potential of ageing population in the regions, particular in the cities				
Bax & Company	Industry			Catalonia
Vall d'Hebron Institute of Research	Other	Consortium		Catalonia
Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund Ortsverband Hamburg-Ne	Other	nonprofit organization		Hamburg
Małopolski Urząd Wojewódzki	Government			Kraków
Internationaler Bund Polska	Other	NGO		Kraków
public administration - MUW Kraków	Government			Kraków
AEMA foundation	Other	FOUNDATION		Catalonia
PARC SANITARI PERE VIRGILI	Other	consortium		Catalonia
Fundacja Klaster LifeScience Kraków	Other	NGO		Kraków
Fundacja Wspomagająca Wychowanie ARCHEXJ	Civil Society			Kraków
Miejski Ośrodek Pomocy Społecznej w Krakowie	Government			Kraków
Institut Investigació Innovació Parc Taulí	Academy			Catalonia
CEAPP UJ	Academy			Kraków
Challenge 2: Improve the lack of transparency & promote a better communication between sector				
HAW Hamburg	Academy			Hamburg
UKE	Academy			Hamburg
Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU, Jagielloni	Academy			Kraków
Krakow City Hall	Government			Kraków
Barrierefrei Leben e.V.	Other	Show Room, Consulting		Hamburg
Barrierefrei Leben e.V.	Other	Consulting		Hamburg
Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH	Industry			Hamburg
University Medical Department Hamburg	Academy			Hamburg
Małopolska Provincial Office in Krakow	Government			Kraków
The City of Krakow	Government			Kraków
FRDL MISTIA	Civil Society			Kraków
Fundació Salut Empordà	Industry			Catalonia
Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Sozialbehörde	Government			Hamburg
Challenge 3. Health & Wellness for Life. Specific but aligned actions to improve life quality				
Regional Centre for Social Policy in Krakow	Other	self - government		Kraków
Fundacja Klaster LifeScience Kraków	Other	Cluster		Kraków
Public Health Agency	Government			Catalonia
Healthy Cities - Bax&Company	Industry			Catalonia
Fundacio Salut Empordà	Other	Sistema Salut		Catalonia
Consortci Sanitari Alt Penedès-Garraf	Other	Health Professional		Catalonia
FURV	Academy			Catalonia
Senior Lab	Civil Society			Catalonia
Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa	Other	Reserach centre		Catalonia
Memima Baby	Industry			Catalonia
GIROMED INSTITUTE	Academy			Catalonia
Jagiellonian University	Academy			Kraków
Parenting Technologies	Industry			Kraków
Fundació Pere Tarrés	Other	NGO		Catalonia

Figure 7. The list of stakeholders that participated in the Session 2 of the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! event – 40 participants in total

In Figure 7 it is possible to see stakeholders that participated in these inter-regional groups of discussion, namely their sectors and regions. However, the distribution per subgroup was not always equal as the distribution of stakeholders was **made based on the participant expressed interest** – by Google form previously to the event. We could see that even if the choice was free, the stakeholders tended to gravitate towards the Challenge that initially was identified by their regional Key Stakeholders, even if that was not the goal.

There are advantages in both situations, either in being in a more trans-regional subgroup or in a more regional subgroup of discussion.

In the case of the groups that were in its majority stakeholders from their own region it showed that the **regions were searching for connections with peers from their region** from other sectors of the ecosystem and could seize this opportunity to exchange ideas and know other regional peers, getting to know more about their needs and views.

On another view we also tackled the **opportunity to put in contact with stakeholders from different regions as the inter-regional discussion** allowed the stakeholders to see other realities, views, examples of strategies and tools, as well as have a wider view of the well-being and healthy living sector, with European challenges that link to regional challenges.

The choices of the stakeholders and results were in both cases positive and revealed different needs and stages of engagement in the regions that helped a better clarity and understanding of the ecosystem for INTEGER partners.

2.2.3.1 Facilitators

The facilitators volunteer from the Project partners. In some cases, it was one facilitator and in other cases, it was two, with the following distribution:

Challenge 1

- Facilitator: Agnieszka Włodaczyk, Project Manager from Krakow Technology Park (Kraków, Poland)
- Facilitator: Jolanta Perek-Białas, Head of the Center for Evaluation and Analysis of Public Policies at the Institute of Sociology at Jagiellonian University (Kraków, Poland)

Challenge 2

- Facilitator: Rachel Stenner, Project Manager, EU Projects Manager at the Ministry of Social Affairs (Hamburg, Germany)

Challenge 3

- Facilitator: Rafel Nualart, Senior Innovation Project Manager at i2Cat (Catalonia, Spain)
- Facilitator: Carla Brito, Innovation Project Manager at i2Cat (Catalonia, Spain)

The main role of the facilitators is to follow up and support the process of collaboration and co-creation between the subgroups stakeholders, especially between session 1 and session 2 of the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* event.

We can resume the facilitator role in the following points:

- Support challenge groups to advance and sharpen ideas and bring stakeholders together
- Share interesting information
- Follow up on what is happening and answer queries
- Contact other actors on the platform or invite new identified ones to join
- Get people involved
- Organise dynamics to build interpersonal trust

The subgroups were organized by the interest of the stakeholder, not by Region at this stage, therefore the subgroups were not only trans-sectoral, as trans-regional and could not be balanced as its distribution was based on their choice per Challenge.

The discussion had a starting point in session 1 and was followed up by a discussion in the platform that had a wrap-up in session 2. The proposals per subgroup were based on questions proposed by the REMEDIES Consortium and managed by the facilitators, as presented previously, although each group ended up following a slightly adjusted methodology to the way of working and thinking of its members.

2.2.3.2 Results of the sub workgroups per challenge

Each Subgroup worked in its own challenge, one from the suggested initial 3, with the orientation of a facilitator from the INTEGER project, in the context of the rationale and role described above.

As it was introduced in the previous section, it is interesting to highlight that even if all had the same tools the results were presented in different formats. As a result of the different actors' interactions, even so the most important was the outcome and the opportunity of interacting, as a first contact with the INTEGER project in this context and their integration in the project's collaborative platform. Therefore, the result, as an initial model of interaction, was very positive and clarifying.

All the subgroups had access to a common platform (Miro & INTEGER platform), by Challenge, having the facilitator as the lead part that enabled and promoted the exchange of ideas. This is the resumed result of the discussions from the 3 subgroups, each dedicated to one of the 3 identified challenges.

- **Challenge 1: How to channel the unused potential of ageing population in the regions, particular in the cities?**

Regarding subgroup that dedicated their analysis to the Challenge 1 the approach was made by challenge proposal and replied to the guideline questions as one joint group. Therefore, the presentation of the results will be made by proposal with a conclusion taken from the replies of the guideline questions. In challenge 1 the subgroup agreed on at least 5 solutions in so-called day/activity centres for senior people, most of them pointing to running solutions that can serve as positive examples to replicate and improve.

The first proposal was focused on the Healthy Cities Generator (HCG)³ solution, as an open free tool that exists and can be improved in order to fully reply to the challenge, namely by broaden its scope and functionalities to focus in social aspects or contribute to promote urban planning in the area of health. The main gap identified in the existent solution, as a public tool, is engaging and co-creating with the ageing population the design and planning process to foster the health promotion in all sectors of the community. This need of interconnection between sector to create positive outcomes on health is the key message on this first proposal. More details of the notes written by the team during the exercise can be consulted in the below figure.

³ <https://healthycitiesgenerator.com/>; introduction video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cU11OoV0NRI&t=6s>;

Figure 8. The first solution proposal for Challenge 1

The second proposal also highlights an existent solution; however it also suggests improvements to it. The solution presented is a long-term program “Senior+”⁴ that is implemented by local authorities in Krakow city (Poland). This program provides services to senior citizens from physical activities to care-offer, depending on the identified needs.

The proposal is for the local government to apply for a grant from the central government Program. The grants are available to all units of local government. Financial support can be obtained for the creation and/or equipment of the “Senior +” day care centres and to function of existing “Senior +” day care centres. This is a very popular program, operating since 2015, as a result of this program 103 Seniors centres have been established.

This project provides the following:

- creation conditions for active ageing;
- security of local government funds to the crate of multiple tasks;
- development of local forms of senior day care;
- activities for intergenerational solidarity of seniors;
- support of seniors’ integration;
- improving the quality of senior’s life in a family and local community;
- involving seniors in family and local community life.

⁴ <https://senior.gov.pl/>

This public project is proposed as a good solution to be used as replicable model, taking in to account it has been successfully implemented by the local government.

Figure 9. The second solution proposal for Challenge 1

The third solution proposed as a reply to the identified challenge 1 is the Centre of Senior's Activity, which was identified also as a good model to link with HCG, presented as the first solution. This would extend this co-creation process to the urban environments the participants live in to identify barriers/facilitators in how they use and move around these spaces and plan for more inclusive, health-promoting environments. This solution focuses on the active integration of senior people in volunteer activities giving them the opportunity not only to contribute to society, to cultural and social activities, as to establish new relationships.

Figure 10. The third solution proposal for Challenge 1

The fourth answer to the challenge question was given in a more transversal and broader way, by indicating “cooperation”, in this sense it indicated the links that could be applied to the existing solution, with focus on the examples in Krakow, presenting ways to implemented this cooperation strategy, as a creation of a database of volunteering adapted to the age group, as well the organization of social campaigns that highlight the role of seniors and use their potential and knowledge, providing training in IT to allow better integration of seniors in the digital world. More details can be accessed in the figure below.

Figure 11. The fourth solution proposal for Challenge 1

The fifth and final solution presented by the subgroup to the Challenge 1 is the *Halo Active 60+ by Strategic Advisory center* that presents a solution that tackles loneliness, as an innovative form of social inclusion of the senior people. This would be a good example to developing a national model for strengthening the social activity of the seniors, with a preparation, launch and management of a senior call centre (served by senior volunteers). Participants are able to meet new friends, broaden their passions and share with others, take care of their physical health, and support and serve each other. The figure below shows some of the notes of the construction of this interactive exchange of ideas reading this proposal.

Figure 12. The fifth solution proposal for Challenge 1⁵

Regarding the analysis of the solutions at light of questions of the guideline for the subgroups the stakeholders of the subgroup concluded that their solutions answer the needs of most of the senior people that are not active and need to be. As the solutions presented target not only the active seniors but also those that are not active and need to be, incentivizing them to socialise, learn and contribute to society by making them interested in using available solutions that replies to their daily needs. It is also identified that the solutions presented need for its development the reinforcement of their infrastructure, staff, regular and solid financing to fill in the gap from business and technology perspective. Another important point highlighted is the policymakers' will (decision) to activate all possible synergies within 4Helix ecosystem to reach the solution to the identified challenge, as there are good examples running with sustainable & replicable potential.

- **Challenge 2: Improve the lack of transparency & promote a better communication between sector**

The approach of Challenge 2 subgroup was simplified, as the guideline questions was summarised in 3 brainstorm activities that addressed points of discussion:

1. **Existing solutions** - identify social innovation solutions that presently exist with transversal & replicable solutions;
2. **Overcome gaps** - overcome the existing gap between social and business-driven innovations;

⁵ Reference link in the work platform: <https://eurohealthnet.eu/list-of-members/>

3. Build 4Helix relations – The building of interpersonal relationship is very important to enable the co-creation of new quadruple helix dynamic

Figure 13. The board to collect ideas from the brainstorming exercise in the subgroup of Challenge 2, led by HAM

Regarding point 1, on existing solutions, the identified social innovation solutions with transversal & replicable solutions were a few, namely:

- The platform of cooperation “Made in Malopolska”⁶
- The symposium “Even more, even more colourful, even more innovative – advancing Hamburg’s forms of residential care!”⁷
- The “Oberbillwerder”⁸ project, about citizens participating in building projects, open dialogue with citizens.
- “Citizens city Lab”⁹ from Hafen City University, which changes cities in the context of digitization with partners from civil society, politics, business and science. It pursues a decidedly interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary perspective by connecting technical issues with social and cultural developments
- Project “Centrum Bremen 2030+ Strategy”¹⁰, where the development process was participatory and took place in close Exchange with the urban community and the inner-city stakeholders.
- HAM-NET, as a network of organizations including citizens, public authorities, academia and industries.

⁶ <https://www.malopolska.pl/samorzad/rady/wojewodzka-rada-dialogu-spolecznego>

⁷ <https://koordination-wohn-pflege-gemeinschaften.hamburg/veranstaltung/fachtag-noch-mehr-noch-bunter-noch-innovativer-hamburger-wohn-pflegeformen-weiter-voranbringen/>

⁸ <https://www.oberbillwerder-hamburg.de/information-beteiligung/>

⁹ <https://www.hcu-hamburg.de/research/csl>

¹⁰ <https://www.bauumwelt.bremen.de/stadtentwicklung/stadtentwicklung/zentrenentwicklung-1267036>

Point 2 of the brainstorming discussion was focused on how to overcome the existing gap between social and business-driven, regarding this question the outputs from the subgroup stakeholders were resumed into the following 3 main ideas:

- a) **Arouse curiosity** to both models and **share knowledge**;
- b) **Establishing trust**, as every participant needs the trust, that his/her idea is "save" and remains to the initiator;
- c) **Make fundings easier** and overcome barriers.

The final point for the brainstorming was dedicated to the analysis of how to build 4Helix relations. One point highlighted was the importance of building interpersonal relationships to enable the co-creation of new quadruple helix Dynamics. Several solutions were arised and shared, as for example:

- a) Involvement of existing networks;
- b) Open space sessions, with diverse participants, in order to visualize challenges and find good solutions;
- c) Apply different formats to create and reinforce relations, from face-to-face to online;
- d) Create the opportunity to "to get to know each other" in random (small) breakout sessions (7 min 3-4 people);
- e) information of partners about the structure of organizations;
- f) Enable the participation on different platforms meetings, websites;
- g) Sessions on mission and vision that every stakeholder share;
- h) Finding an adequate language to ensure understanding with all parties

These three points were the focus of a more informal and less structured form of exchange of ideas and outputs for the INTEGER model creation.

- **Challenge 3: Health & Wellness for Life. Specific but aligned actions to improve life quality**

The stakeholders from Challenge 3 subgroup decided to focus on actions to improve quality of life.

The first questions in the table was:

- 1) What is your MVP (minimum viable product) solution that could answer the challenge in some way?
- 2) What is the objective and resolution of your MVP solution?

The orientation given by the facilitator was that the participants should focus specifically on how social and business-driven innovations can join forces to engage in a clear implementation and possible solution used. Some examples of existing solutions to be taken into account and apply new interconnections and synergies were also mentioned, in the footnote from circles in the Figure below you can access the links to the different examples presented.

Figure 14. The solution proposed and the objective and resolution on Challenge 3¹¹

The second question to be addressed by the subgroups was “What is the target public for your solution?” The focus was mainly on 3 types of public, seniors, migrants and ethnic minorities and people at risk of social exclusion, more details are described in the Figure below.

¹¹ <https://foodcllic.eu/>; <https://healthycitiesgenerator.com/>; <https://www.seniorlab.eu/>

Figure 15. The target public identified in Challenge 3

On the third question the stakeholders from the Challenge 3 subgroup addressed the question regarding synergies that could contribute to the solution implementation across the 4 Helix. The perspective is not to create new links but to use the existing solutions in a more effective way that would benefit the outcome of the challenge. As it is possible to see in the below figure, solutions as execution of small pilots with the 4 helix participants and Exchange of know-how and best practices between the 3 Helix stakeholders is foreseen, in order to find more efficiency through the better channel of communication and exchange of mutual experience, valuing the contribution of each stakeholder in the 4 Helix.

Figure 16. The identified synergies to be implemented in the solution presented in Challenge 3

The fourth question that had to be approached regarding the solution proposal for the Challenge 3 subgroup is dedicated to the novelty, the change, the point that would be in the heart of this solution proposal as an added value of the well-being and healthy living ecosystem, that could bring market value as well. In this regard the processes were the main novelty, a new intervention and connection, namely the integration of the view of the users, the people that were the target of the final objective and impact positively in the multiple health determinants and urban planning strategies.

Figure 17. The change and solution identified in the proposed solution for Challenge 3

Question 5 is dedicated to the sustainability of the solution and replicability, essential for the market value and added value for the solution and the INTEGER Project. In this point the stakeholders highlighted the barriers, namely the public health funding and the need to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of the solution. Here we can also apply the needs of the above-mentioned pilots that could answer and precise this goal. Although it indicated some pathways, such as the need to involve more diverse sectors in the public health sector to reach the goal of sustainability and replicability, namely also the interaction with other sectors, as private funding, that can be either from the private sector, as well as from citizens, for example.

Figure 18. Analysis of the sustainable and replicable aspects of the solution proposed for Challenge 3

The last question links the solution with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), in order to be aligned with a wider context of solution that contributes to global needs. In the case of Challenge 3 it was identified the link between the solution and the SDG in 7 goals that are linked with the SDG: 1. Good wealth and well-being (goal 3); 2. Quality education (goal 4); 3. Gender equality (goal 5); 4. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (goal 9); 5. Reduced Inequality (goal 10); 6. Sustainable Cities and Communities (goal 11) and finally, 7. Partnerships to achieve the Goal (goal 17).

Figure 19. SDG goal and its link to the solution proposed for Challenge 3

3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

This task has a close link to several tasks and deliverables in the Project, we will highlight some of the most relevant.

Task 2.3 is in the context of the WP2, led by HAM, that is closely linked with O1 of the INTEGER Project to catalyse emerging 3H&4H integration ecosystems' models.

In the context of WP2 the Task 2.3 has a direct link and impact on the Task 2.4 *Collaborathon results exploitation*, to be implemented in the following months - M5-M12 – that previews the collection of solutions proposed, synthesising lessons learned and implementation of actual actions to generate scenarios, as exploitation action linked with other WP's in the project, namely the WP4, for the bi-directional inclusion of socio-digital innovators and entrepreneurs in innovation ecosystems. Both tasks are led by F6S.

WP3

Regarding the synergies with WP3, the model event will serve as a step to collect and implement tools, strategies and methodologies that serve as a blueprint to be implemented in the regional events previewed in WP3, namely on Task 3.3 *Piloting the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital projects via regional Collaborathons*, previewed for M13-24, in a co-leading between F6S & URV (laeder of the Work Package. This task previewed the selection of three best social projects at each region (URV, HAM & UJ), by

a) Recruit regional key stakeholders with expertise in the assessment of business concepts or potential business opportunities; b) Setup of evaluation criteria, design the expert's evaluation template and deploy the experts briefing; c) Deploy an online pitching session for projects presentation, Q&A and selection. This will be the culmination of an initial process of analysis and engagement started with Task 2.3 and the overall works developed in WP2.

Figure 20. Interaction between activities in WP2 and WP3

WP4

The platform that was used during the events as an exploitation and collaboration measure implemented through the events promoted in the context of the Task 2.3.

By engaging the stakeholders in the INTEGER platform, as a kick start action of WP4, we contributed for synergies with the WP4, especially in the Task 4.1, by supporting the gathering and systematisation of relevant information and material in the INTEGER platform hub, with the societal challenges and needs as identified by the Collaboratory dynamics and other regions dynamics and identification of relevant stakeholders from the 4Helix. Under the Task 2.3 a first discussion on challenges and needs started and promoted the start on a long-lasting initiative on a model of bi-directional inclusive dynamics and mechanisms of workable processes of stakeholders & local and regional social innovator actors of the well-being and healthy living ecosystem, in the context of the INTEGER project's platform.

WP5

Communication is always essential in the support of any project activity and in this case that is not different. We would highlight mainly the Task 5.2 on the *Stakeholder engagement and liaison with relevant initiatives*, as it contributed with the mapping of the key stakeholders towards the creation of a pan-European facilitated community of interest, gathering stakeholders from different countries around the topics of INTEGER, supporting the regional partners and following up the actions and supporting its implementation.

4 Lessons learned

This task is implementing new principals and initial actions. Therefore, it is based on experimental collaboration which means in order to learn and implement more efficient actions to be able to scale up and connect different kinds of innovations. Several lessons were taken from the process and we resume in the following, by assessing importance, from the one that had more impact in the action to the less:

- **More time to engage stakeholders**

The INTEGER collaborative platform, as a work dynamic, was proposed as a follow-up tool of discussion for the subgroups, from session 1 to session 2, to reach a joint proposal and present in the context of the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Event*, however, this social innovation journey had to be adjusted, as the participants did not engage and were as much as active as expected in the INTEGER platform. Therefore, we had to rely on the time during the live sessions to make decisions in groups and have the needed outcomes from this event. Although we created the profile of facilitator, the dynamisation of the process encountered the barrier of the stakeholders that were not motivated enough, as the stakeholders were not as responsive as required to create this community feeling and be able to have the needed outcomes. **The use of the INTEGER platform by itself in such a short time did not enable the needed engagement from the participants so that we could have the results we needed from the subgroup of discussions.**

It was identified that there was a gap in time and engagement when moving from the regional sphere to the inter-regional sphere. The time to build trust at a regional level was not enough, in overall regions, to be able to advance to the inter-regional process of co-creation. As this task was foreseen to be implemented in the very early beginning of the Project and for a very short period there was not enough time to engage stakeholders and connect with facilitators, not only in their region, as well, and mostly with facilitators from other regions. This was also a barrier to going beyond the regional sphere, limiting the inclusion of international stakeholders in the process.

The way that this lack of trust and engagement was expressed in a specific barrier in the process of implementation of the task, was, for example, the lack of engagement in the INTEGER platform. This required an adjustment in the initial plan, before the event, as organising a closed, per invitation, model of the event. Where the partner would create a list of participants and advance themselves with the invitation

The conclusion was that the INTEGER platform provides a connection of the community of actors towards co-creation. However, it can only be used in certain actions, not being very useful in an initial process of engaging and building trust, as it is only a written platform, providing a low level of mutual knowledge as a starting point of connection. We realised that stakeholders needed more icebreaker exercises, in person, or live online to be able to fully take advantage of the INTEGER platform.

- **Availability of the stakeholders**

Another point was the time available to produce the intended results between sessions, even with the effort of the facilitators, as well as the availability of the stakeholders to be present in the 2 sessions,

booked a week apart, one as a presentation and the other as the presentation of results. The intention was to give time to add another tool, such as the INTEGER platform, and develop the relationship over time between stakeholders, at a trans-sectoral and trans-regional level. As the tasks were only to be planned and implemented in 2 months it was quite a short time to invite and count on the availability of the stakeholders in such short notice.

- **Different expectations that reflect different levels of regional engagement**

Another point that was identified as a lesson learned is the identification of the barrier that the different regions, with different expectations, presented as a challenge, as each region is at a different level of need. For example, the regions had different levels of engagement to start the process with. Hamburg region needed a higher regional engagement between stakeholders, as Catalonia has a high level of inter-regional engagement and expected to reach a higher level of inter-regional connections and are not so motivated in engaging at regional level. Therefore, these nuances have to be taken into account and compensated for moving forward in the future actions taken by the project.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The reinforcement of communication between regions and peers from the 4Helix on the healthy living and well-being area, creating awareness regarding the common needs in the economic and social innovation ecosystems, was a first step through the activities initiated in Task 2.3. These events were the start of developing a peer-to-peer approach to joint digital actions in order to support social innovation entrepreneurs and start-ups and open them to a larger network, beyond their region to other social innovation SMEs, investors, corporates and other actors within the healthy living and well-being area ecosystem that could provide direct support or benefit from their innovation.

The deliverable 2.2 *Collaborathon Report & Exploitation Plan* is an initial package of actions that were implemented with the goal of contributing to a new generation of a 4Helix labs that enables new ways of connecting and replying to the new European paradox and the citizens' demands and needs, as a starting point of actions that reach out to the stakeholders and invite them to engage in INTEGER project. These initiatives were created as checkpoints of a joint larger network of bridges, having in mind the added value for the participants being part of a vibrant '*glocal*' community building long-term collaborations in physical, virtual and hybrid mode, along the INTEGER Project events and initiatives.

Figure 21. INTEGER Model Core Group space in the platform

Hence, the following steps are:

- the compilation of the feedback and documents of the definition of the Model, and
- the preparation of the workshop during the ENOLL Living Lab Days
- the constitution of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory

Figure 24. ENOLL Open Living lab Days event

It has been important the identification of champions and early adopters, stakeholders with the vision aligned with INTEGER (systemic transformation).

These actors have expressed their commitment with time and active participation to support in early stages of defining the INTEGER Model. During the process some reached as directly through different means (platform, LinkedIn, phone calls, or explicit offer during the meetings). This gave rise to build the Model Core Group and to start discussing the identified features and tentative modules of the Model.

This led to the implementation of the group in the platform and the celebration of 2 targeted sessions of the core group. One already took place on the 26th June and the other will be on the 10th July.

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ANNEX 1 - INTEGER GA

Key Stakeholders event power point

<p>10h30 Welcome notes <i>Toni Caro, coordinator, i2CAT (5 m)</i></p> <p>10h35 Project presentation <i>Toni Caro, coordinator, i2CAT (10 m)</i></p> <p>10h45 Context, methodology & goals of this pre-event initiative & presentation of the results of the google form <i>Lina Silveira F6S Project Manager (15 m)</i></p> <p>11h00 Group gathering, per region, for brainstorming on the challenge to be chosen <i>Moderated by a regional partner of the project (40 m)</i></p> <p>11h40 Presentation of the result of the discussion, main group presentations. <i>Presented by the regional partner that moderated the group session, moderated by F6S (30 m)</i></p> <p>12h10 Towards a 'Col-laboratori model- pathway for a joint definition, <i>Toni Caro, coordinator, i2CAT (15 m)</i></p> <p>12h25 Closing remarks <i>i2CAT & F6S (5 m)</i></p>	<p>Key Stakeholder event Meeting Agenda 18th April 2023 (CEST – Brussels time)</p>
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ANNEX 2 - F6S Power Point from the INTEGER Kick off Meeting

Key Stakeholder Google form results

Google form results from Key stakeholders event (18th of April 2023):

- profile of participants: sector; region
- Challenge choice: general & per region

Google form results - Sectors

Key Stakeholders by sector

Key stakeholder sector represented in Kraków

Key stakeholder sector represented in Hamburg

Key stakeholder sector represented in Catalonia

Google form results on challenge/need - General

Global result (3 regions): What is, in your view the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region? Taking in consideration physical, mental and social well-being.

Google form results on challenge/need - Catalonia

Catalonia: What is, in your view the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region?
Taking in consideration physical, mental and social well-being.

Google form results on challenge/need - Hamburg

Hamburg: What is, in your view the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region?
Taking in consideration physical, mental and social well-being.

Google form results on challenge/need - Kraków

Kraków: What is, in your view the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region?
Taking in consideration physical, mental and social well-being.

ANNEX 3 - Guidelines Key Stakeholder Pre-event

Guidelines Key Stakeholder Pre-event

Guidelines

Key Stakeholder Pre-event – subgroups of discussion

18.04.2023

1. After different debates and contrasts with our stakeholders in Catalonia, it was narrowed down the broad theme of health and well-being into 5 general topics:

- a. *Ageing*
- b. *Pollution & healthy cities*
- c. *Nutrition*
- d. *Social/laboral inclusion*
- e. *Physical exercise*

2. The choice of the challenge should take into consideration the following points:

It should be...

- specific to your region;
- wide enough to be transversal, but focused enough that a specific solution can help mitigate it;
- aligned with the Sustainable Development goals;
- Not too generic, as it should be focused enough to result into real solutions/products/policies/actions, that a specific solution can help mitigate it;
- define a regional challenge, but they must have in mind if the problem can be common for other regions (this may suggest certain scalability of the potential solution).

3. Questions to be aware, to reflect and direct to a decision

1. Please specify your biggest challenge in your work linked with social innovations in your region?
2. Please indicate what is your ideal way of working with others (as partners) for supporting social innovation development in your region?
3. How to create a long term strategy for bridging social, business and digital oriented innovation? (name concrete activities, name the concrete key authors and assign responsibilities)
4. How to make the cooperation of social, digital and business oriented innovators alive, stable and sustainable and well positioned in regional strategies?
5. How could the project help to connect stakeholders in the regions? What could be the benefit out of the project for innovators? What challenges do you think the project could experience?
6. How to involve all parties to solve problems together? How to simplify communication and make it transparent?
7. How domains defined in the 'age-friendly city' concept developed by WHO interrelate? E.g. name at least one causal relationship between each.
8. What exactly do you would like to solve or to work within your field/area of knowledge? What is your unique know-how that you think it could bring a fresh approach together with other potential stakeholders?

OUTPUT: The group has to reach the decision on one challenge/need to be presented in the **Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!**

ANNEX 4 - F6S Power Points from Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Session 1

AGENDA SESSION 1 of the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*

Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!

DAY I: 17th May, 2023 (1-2)

Meeting Agenda (CEST – Brussels time)

10h30 – Welcome notes, Toni Caro, i2Cat, as INTEGER coordinator (5m)

10h35 – Overall presentation of the agenda, landscape of the participants & goal of the event, *Lina Silveira, F6S (15m)*

10h50 – Presentation of results from the Key stakeholders event (15m)

- Presentation of challenge 1, *Maria Wojtacha from Internationaler Bund Polska*
- Presentation of challenge 2, *Christina Lindemann, Coordinator HAM-NET, University Hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf*
- Presentation of challenge 3, *Rosina Malagrida, head of the Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa (Catalonia)*

Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!

DAY I: 17th May, 2023 (2-2)

Meeting Agenda (CEST – Brussels time)

10h55 – Let's dive into our digital collaborative space - the INTEGER platform:

- What's there for me?
- Let's co-create innovative win-wins
- INTEGER's platform (theglobal.network) - Beyond another conventional social media-Helix actors interacting and co-creating, Toni Caro, i2CAT (15m)

11h10 – Groups gathering and presentations within the groups (15m)

11h25 – Presentation of the first training pill - What the role of a facilitator entails to boost 4 Helix collaborations and social and business driven innovations to meet and merge? Towards the Col-laber profile, Toni Caro, i2CAT / Afedemy (10m)

11h35 - Inspirational talk, Raffaella Seitz, project manager, Cross Innovation Hub (Hamburg) (15m)

11h50 – Closing notes, *Toni Caro, i2Cat, as INTEGER coordinator (5m)*

ANNEX 5 - F6S Power Points from Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Session 2

AGENDA SESSION 2 of the *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!*

Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!

DAY II: 25th May, 2023

Meeting Agenda (CEST - Brussels time)

10h30 – Welcome note, present the agenda, Toni Caro, I2Cat & Lina Silveira, F6S (10m)

10h40 - Towards a solution!: discussion per challenge in each subgroups (40m)

11h20 – Presentation of solution by each lead of the subgroup, per challenge, in an elevator pitch model (about 5/7m each) (25m)

11h45 -Forum of discussion & Q&A with Facilitators and key stakeholders, moderated by Lina Silveira, F6S (15m)

12h00 – What is the Key value added for INTEGER? What is new? What comes next?, *Toni Caro, I2Cat (15M)*

12h15 – Closing notes, Kai Schnackenberg, HAM, and Toni Caro, I2Cat (10m)

ANNEX 6 - Report questions to Facilitators for Key stakeholders work outputs

Google form results on the challenges

ANNEX 7 - Report questions to Facilitators for Key stakeholders work outputs

Innovation 4Healthy living | *Let's Hack together!*

17th & 25th of May

Report for group work outputs

NAME OF THE CHALLENGE:

Questions to be replied shortly, but clearly, by the group regarding their solution:

- 1) What is the objective and the resolution of your solution? Please focus specifically on how the social and the business-driven innovations can join forces to engage in a clear implementation and the possible solution to be used.
- 2) *Who is the target public of your solution?*
- 3) *What are the synergies that will be implemented in the 4Helix to contribute for the solution implementation?*
- 4) *What change do this solution will bring, as an added value for the well-being and healthy leaving ecosystem?*
- 5) *Is your solution sustainable & replicable?*
- 6) *In what way your solution replies to the SDG goals?*